

DESCRIPTION OF LOCAL DERIVATIONS ON LOW-DIMENSIONAL JORDAN ALGEBRAS

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The present paper is devoted to local derivations on Jordan algebras. The Gleason – Kahane – Zelazko theorem is a basis of the concept of local derivations. This theorem is a fundamental contribution in the theory of Banach algebras. The concept of local derivations was introduced and studied by R. Kadison. He proved that each continuous local derivation from a von Neumann algebra into its dual Banach bmodule is a derivation. Later, B. Jonson extended the above result by proving that every local derivation from a C^* – algebra into its Banach bimodule is a derivation. In particular, Johnson proved that local derivations of a C^* – algebra A into a Banach A –bimodule X are continuous even if not assumed a priori to be so.

It is known that every local derivation on a JB –algebra is a derivation. In [2] Nuriddinov (the author of the present paper) gave the description of local derivations on five – dimensional nilpotent associative Jordan algebras. Also, in [3] Nuriddinov and Urinbayev gave the description of local derivations on four – dimensional nilpotent noncommutative Jordan algebras over C . Arzikulov and Nuriddinov gave the description of local derivations on five-dimensional nilpotent nonassociative Jordan algebras in [4].

In the present paper I give the description of local derivations on Jordan algebras of dimension less than or equal to four.

Let J be a Jordan algebra of dimension four over an algebraically closed field \mathbb{F} of characteristic $\neq 2$ with a basis $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$. Let x be an element in J . Then $x = x_1 e_1 + x_2 e_2 + x_3 e_3 + x_4 e_4$, for some elements x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 in \mathbb{F} . Throughout of the paper let $\vec{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)^{Tr}$. Conversely, if $v = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)^{Tr}$ is a column vector with x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 in F , then, throughout of the paper, by $b v$ we will denote the element $x_1 e_1 + x_2 e_2 + x_3 e_3 + x_4 e_4$, i.e., $\hat{v} = x_1 e_1 + x_2 e_2 + x_3 e_3 + x_4 e_4$.

Definition. Recall that a linear mapping D on a Jordan algebra J , satisfying, for each pair x, y of elements in J , $D(xy) = D(x)y + xD(y)$, is called a derivation, and a linear mapping $\nabla: J \rightarrow J$ is called a local derivation if for every $x \in J$ there exists a derivation $D: J \rightarrow J$ such that $\nabla(x) = D_x(x)$.

Let J_{45} be the Jordan algebra with a basis $\{e_1, n_1, n_2, n_3\}$ defined in [1]. In this algebra, the multiplication table is defined as follows:

$$n_1^2 = n_3^2 = n^2, e_1 n_1 = \frac{1}{2} n_1$$

Theorem. Each local derivation of the Jordan algebra J_{45} is a derivation.

Proof. Let ∇ be a local derivation on J_{45} . Then

$$\nabla(x) = \sum_{j=1}^4 b_{1,j} x_j e_1 + \sum_{i=2}^4 \left(\sum_{j=1}^4 b_{i,j} x_j \right) n_{i-1}, x \in J_{45}$$

for the matrix $B = (b_{i,j})_{i,j=1}^4$ of the local derivation ∇ , where $x = x_1 e_1 + x_2 n_1 + x_3 n_2 + x_4 n_3$ and $x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 \in \mathbb{F}$. By the definition for any element $x \in J_{45}$ there exists a derivation D_x such that $\nabla(x) = D_x(x)$.

$$D_x(x) = \alpha_x x_2 n_1 + (\beta_x x_1 + 2\alpha_x x_3 + \gamma_x x_4) n_2 + \alpha_x x_4 n_3, x \in J_{45}$$

for some elements α_x, β_x and γ_x in \mathbb{F} , depending on x .

If we take $x = e_1$, then $\nabla(e_1) = D_{e_1}(e_1) = \beta_{e_1} n_2$. On the other hand, $\nabla(e_1) = b_{1,1} e_1 + b_{2,1} n_1 + b_{3,1} n_2 + b_{4,1} n_3$. Hence, $b_{1,1} = 0, b_{2,1} = 0, b_{3,1} = \beta_{e_1}, b_{4,1} = 0$. Similarly we get $b_{1,2} = 0, b_{2,2} = \alpha_{n_1}, b_{3,2} = 0, b_{4,2} = 0$, if we take $x = n_1$. Also, we analogously get $b_{1,3} = 0, b_{2,3} = 0, b_{3,3} = 2\alpha_{n_2}, b_{4,3} = 0, b_{1,4} = 0, b_{2,4} = 0, b_{3,4} = \gamma_{n_3}, b_{4,4} = \alpha_{n_3}$.

Now, since ∇ is linear we have $\nabla(n_1 + n_2) = \nabla(n_1) + \nabla(n_2)$. From this it follows that

$$\nabla(n_1 + n_2) = \alpha_{n_1+n_2} n_1 + 2\alpha_{n_1+n_2} n_2 = \alpha_{n_1} n_1 + 2\alpha_{n_2} n_2$$

Hence, $\alpha_{n_1+n_2} = \alpha_{n_1}, \alpha_{n_1+n_2} = \alpha_{n_2}$ and $\alpha_{n_1} = \alpha_{n_2}$.

Similarly, from the equality $\nabla(n_1 + n_3) = \nabla(n_1) + \nabla(n_3)$ we get $\alpha_{n_1} = \alpha_{n_2}$.

Since the local derivation ∇ was chosen arbitrarily, we have it has the following form

$$\nabla(x) = \alpha_{n_1} x_2 n_1 + (\beta_{e_1} x_1 + 2\alpha_{n_1} x_3 + \gamma_{n_3} x_4) n_2 + \alpha_{n_1} x_4 n_3, x \in J_{45}$$

where α, β, γ belong to \mathbb{F} .

Let $\nabla(x) = \widehat{B}x, x \in J_{45}$. We suppose that for each $a \in J_{45}$ there exists a derivation of the form a matrix A_a such that

$$\nabla(a) = \widehat{A}a = \widehat{A}_a a.$$

We find the form of the matrix A , for which the map, defined by the matrix A is a local derivation. For this propose we consider the following system of linear equations

$$\begin{cases} a_2\alpha_a = a_2\alpha \\ a_1\beta_a + 2a_3\alpha_a + a_4\gamma_a = a_1\beta + 2a_3\alpha + a_4\gamma \\ a_4\alpha_a = a_4\alpha \end{cases}$$

with respect to the variables $\alpha_a, \beta_a, \gamma_a$ for each $a \in J_{45}$. Here, α, β, γ are elements from F . Note that, if the left part of any equation of the system is equal to zero, then the right part of this equation is also equal to zero.

Now, suppose that $a_1 \neq 0, a_2 \neq 0$ and $a_3 = 0$. Then we have

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_a = \alpha \\ \beta_a = \frac{a_4}{a_1} (\gamma - \gamma_a) \end{cases}$$

This system has a solution for any $a_1 \neq 0, a_2 \neq 0, a_3 = 0$.

Now, suppose that $a \neq 0$. Then we have

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_a = \alpha \\ \gamma_a = \frac{a_1}{a_4} (\beta - \beta_a) + \frac{2a_3}{a_4} (\alpha - \alpha_a) + \gamma \end{cases}$$

This system has a solution.

Thus we have

$$\nabla(x) = \alpha x_2 e_1 + (\beta x_1 + 2\alpha x_3 + \gamma x_4) n_2 + \alpha x_4 n_3$$

But this coincides with the form (1.1) of a derivation on J_{45} . This completes the proof.

Let J_{63} be the Jordan algebra defined in [1] with a basis $\{e_1, n_1, n_2, n_3\}$ such that

$$n_1^2 = n_4^2 = n_2, n_1 n_2 = n_3$$

Theorem. A linear operator ∇ on the Jordan algebra J_{63} is a local derivation if and only if this linear operator belongs to the following subspace

$$\text{LocDer}(J_{63}) = \{E_{1,1} - \frac{1}{3}E_{1,4} + 2E_{2,2} - \frac{1}{3}E_{2,4} - \frac{1}{3}E_{4,1} + E_{4,4}, \\ E_{2,1} - E_{2,4}, E_{3,1}, E_{3,2}, E_{3,3}, E_{3,4}\}.$$

Proof. Let J_{63} be the Jordan algebra over the field F taken with the basis $\{n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4\}$. First we prove that the matrix of each local derivation on J_{63} has the matrix form.

Let ∇ be an arbitrary local derivation on J_{63} . Then

$$\nabla(x) = \sum_{i=1}^4 \left(\sum_{j=1}^4 a_{i,j} x_j \right) e_i, x \in J_{63}$$

for the matrix $A = (a_{i,j})_{i,j=1}^4$ of the local derivation ∇ , where $x = x_1 n_1 + x_2 n_2 +$

$x_3 n_3 + x_4 n_4$. By the definition, for any element $x \in \mathcal{J}_{63}$, there exists a derivation D_x such that $\nabla(x) = D_x x = \widehat{A}x$.

$$D_x(x) = \widehat{A}x = \left(\alpha_x x_1 - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_x x_4 \right) n_1 + \left(\beta_x x_1 + 2\alpha_x x_2 + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_x - \beta_x \right) \right) n_2 + \\ + \left(\gamma_x x_1 + 2\beta_x x_2 + \frac{8}{3} \alpha_x x_3 + \delta_x x_4 \right) n_3 + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_x x_1 + \alpha_x x_4 \right) n_4,$$

where $\alpha_x, \beta_x, \gamma_x$ and δ_x in F , depending on x .

Using equalities $\nabla(n_i) = D_{n_i}(n_i) = \widehat{A}_{n_i} n_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ we get $a_{1,1} = \alpha_{n_1}$, $a_{2,1} = \beta_{n_1}, a_{3,1} = \gamma_{n_1}, a_{4,1} = -\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1}, a_{1,2} = 0, a_{2,2} = 2\alpha_{n_2}, a_{3,2} = 2\beta_{n_2}, a_{4,2} = 0, a_{1,3} = 0, a_{2,3} = 0, a_{3,3} = \frac{8}{3} \alpha_{n_3}, a_{4,3} = 0, a_{1,4} = -\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_4}, a_{2,4} = -\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_4} - \beta_{n_4}, a_{3,4} = \delta_{n_4}, a_{4,4} = \alpha_{n_4}$.

Now, since ∇ is linear we have $\nabla(n_1 + n_4) = \nabla(n_1) + \nabla(n_4)$. From this it follows that

$$\nabla(n_1 + n_4) = \left(\alpha_{n_1+n_4} - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1+n_4} \right) n_1 + \left(\beta_{n_1+n_4} - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1+n_4} - \beta_{n_1+n_4} \right) n_2 + \\ + \left(\gamma_{n_1+n_4} + \delta_{n_1+n_4} \right) n_3 + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1+n_4} + \alpha_{n_1+n_4} \right) n_4 = \left(\alpha_{n_1} - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_4} \right) n_1 + \\ + \left(\beta_{n_1} - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_4} - \beta_{n_4} \right) n_2 + \left(\gamma_{n_1} + \delta_{n_4} \right) n_3 + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1} + \alpha_{n_4} \right) n_4.$$

Hence $\alpha_{n_1} = \alpha_{n_4}$ and $\beta_{n_1} = \beta_{n_4}$.

How $\nabla(n_1 + n_2 + n_4) = \nabla(n_1) + \nabla(n_2) + \nabla(n_4)$ gives us

$$\nabla(n_1 + n_2 + n_4) = \left(\alpha_{n_1+n_2+n_4} - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1+n_2+n_4} \right) n_1 + \left(\beta_{n_1+n_2+n_4} + \alpha_{n_1+n_2+n_4} - \right. \\ \left. - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1+n_2+n_4} - \beta_{n_1+n_2+n_4} \right) n_2 + \left(\gamma_{n_1+n_2+n_4} + 2\beta_{n_1+n_2+n_4} + \delta_{n_1+n_2+n_4} \right) n_3 + \\ + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1+n_2+n_4} + \alpha_{n_1+n_2+n_4} \right) n_4 = \left(\alpha_{n_1} - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_4} \right) n_1 + \left(\beta_{n_1} + 2\alpha_{n_2} - \right. \\ \left. - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_4} - \beta_{n_4} \right) n_2 + \left(\gamma_{n_1} + 2\beta_{n_2} + \delta_{n_4} \right) n_3 + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1} + \alpha_{n_4} \right) n_4.$$

Hence $\alpha_{n_2} = \alpha_{n_4}$.

So, we have

$$\nabla(x) = \widehat{A}x = \left(\alpha_{n_1} x_1 - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1} x_2 \right) n_1 + \left(\beta_{n_1} x_1 + 2\alpha_{n_1} x_2 + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1} - \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - \beta_{n_1} \right) x_4 \right) n_2 + \left(\gamma_{n_1} x_1 + 2\beta_{n_2} x_2 + \frac{8}{3} \alpha_{n_3} x_3 + \delta_{n_4} x_4 \right) n_3 + \left(-\frac{1}{3} \alpha_{n_1} x_1 + \right. \\ \left. + \alpha_{n_1} x_4 \right) n_4, x \in \mathcal{J}_{63}.$$

Since the local derivation ∇ was chosen arbitrarily, we have it has the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla(x) = \widehat{A}\bar{x} = & \left(\alpha x_1 - \frac{1}{3}\alpha x_2\right)n_1 + \left(\beta x_1 + 2\alpha x_2 + \left(-\frac{1}{3}\alpha - \beta\right)x_4\right)n_2 \\ & + \left(\gamma x_1 + 2\phi x_2 + \frac{8}{3}\psi x_3 + \delta x_4\right)n_3 + \left(-\frac{1}{3}\alpha x_1 + \alpha x_4\right)n_4, x \in \mathcal{J}_{63} \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \phi, \psi$ belong to F .

Let $\nabla(x) = \widehat{A}\bar{x}$, $x \in \mathcal{J}_{63}$. We suppose that for each $a \in \mathcal{J}_{63}$ there exists a derivation of the form a matrix A_a such that

$$\nabla(a) = \widehat{A}\bar{a} = A_a \bar{a}.$$

We find the form of the matrix A , for which the map, defined by the matrix A is a local derivation. For this propose we consider the following system of linear equations

$$\begin{cases} a_1\alpha_a - \frac{1}{3}a_4\alpha_a = a_1\alpha - \frac{1}{3}a_4\alpha \\ a_1\beta_a + 2a_2\alpha_a + a_4\left(-\frac{1}{3}\alpha_a - \beta_a\right) = a_1\beta + 2a_2\alpha + a_4\left(-\frac{1}{3}\alpha - \beta\right) \\ a_1\gamma_a + 2a_2\beta_a + \frac{8}{3}a_3\alpha_a + a_4\delta_a = a_1\gamma + a_2\phi + a_3\psi + a_4\delta \\ -\frac{1}{3}a_1\alpha_a + a_4\alpha_a = -\frac{1}{3}a_1\alpha + a_4\alpha \end{cases}$$

with respect to the variables $\alpha_a, \beta_a, \gamma_a, \delta_a$ for each $a \in \mathcal{J}_{63}$. Here $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \phi, \psi$ are elements from F .

Note that, if the left part of any equation of the last system is equal to zero, then the right part of this equation is also equal to zero.

This system has a solution for any $a_1 \neq 0$ from F and gives a solution of the system.

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_a = \alpha \\ \beta_a = \beta \\ \gamma_a = \gamma + \frac{a_2}{a_1}\phi + \frac{a_3}{a_1}\psi + \frac{a_4}{a_1}\delta - \frac{2a_2}{a_1}\beta - \frac{8a_3}{3a_1}\alpha - \frac{a_4}{a_1}\delta_a \end{cases}$$

If $a_1 = 0, a_4 \neq 0$ then

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_a = \alpha \\ \beta_a = \beta \\ \delta_a = \frac{a_2}{a_4}\phi + \frac{a_3}{a_4}\psi + \delta - \frac{2a_2}{a_4}\beta - \frac{8a_3}{3a_4}\alpha \end{cases}$$

If $a_1 = 0, a_2 \neq 0$ and $a_4 = 0$ then

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_a = \alpha \\ \beta_a = \frac{1}{2}\phi + \frac{a_3}{2a_2}\psi + \frac{a_3}{a_2}\left(-\frac{8}{3}\alpha + \psi\right) \end{cases}$$

and, if $a_1 = 0, a_2 = 0, a_3 \neq 0$ and $a_4 = 0$ then $\alpha_a = \frac{3}{8}\psi$.

Both of these systems have a solution in the appropriate cases and they also give a solution of the system. We have considered all cases of values of parameters a_1, a_2, a_3 and a_4 . Thus, for each element $a \in \mathcal{J}_{63}$, the system of linear equations has a solution.

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